

Mediating Role of Hygiene Ambiance and Customer Satisfaction during ...

Mediating Role of Hygiene Ambiance and Customer Satisfaction during COVID-19: Evidence from university Students of Hyderabad, Pakistan

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Abstract

Aim of this study is mediating effect of ambiance between food quality, brand awareness and customer satisfaction during COVID-19. The quantitative research approach was applied in this study, which utilized primary data and a sample of 222 business students who are consumers of KFC in Hyderabad. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The findings revealed that three partial mediation effect ambiance between food quality, brand awareness and customer satisfaction during COVID-19. Based on these findings it is important it for KFC top management should focus on ambiance in order to get more customer satisfaction during COVID-19.

Keywords: Ambiance, Food quality, Brand awareness, Customer satisfaction

1. Introduction

Restaurant industry is one of the most important sector in every country, number of customers visit different restaurants to gain happiness (Jain and Thakur 2020). The restaurant industry is very saturated. Almost every other day, we hear news of some new restaurant opening up in the city but not every restaurant remains in the market for a longer period of time. There are different parameters on which a restaurant is dependent when we talk about this particular industry. It seems to be a B2C industry but where a product and service both are very much important for customer satisfaction. The first very most important element here is the quality and customer service. If the quality of the food is excellent it is ultimately going to bring business on its own through word of mouth. In this

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digital era, to make a brand or a restaurant popular is not a big deal, reviews and influencers play a huge role in bringing such businesses on the boom or for brand awareness purposes. It is very important for restaurants to know and understand the actual concept of customer satisfaction and how restaurants can improve themselves and how they can meet customer's requirements. Customer satisfaction is the reaction of fulfilling needs of the customers (Ilyas et al., 2020). As food is the crucial part of the restaurant, the food has and will always be having, a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Food quality is considered to be the crucial element that has an impact on customer satisfaction. In customer food choice decisions, the quality itself is one of the crucial matters (Kannan, 2017). Customer satisfaction is very crucial for getting restaurant success if the customers are fully satisfied with food quality, they tend to visit frequently they build good relationship or make a bond with that restaurant (Jain and Thakur 2020).

Abdullah et al., (2018) talked about factors affecting customer satisfaction regarding restaurants and taking into consideration the variables were food quality, service quality and price fairness, how these three factors impact the customer satisfaction in a restaurant, their research is missing one variable that we are taking in our research that is brand awareness, how the brand awareness affects the customer satisfaction in restaurant and knowing about the brand and its reputation how much the customers are satisfied with the specific restaurant of our choice. focus their research on halal certified restaurants in Malaysia as we are only basing our research on one restaurant that is Lamoosh in Hyderabad, Pakistan (Abdullah et al., 2018). Apart from that, Cha, and Borchgrevink, (2018), talk about food safety and its connection to customer satisfaction in restaurants environment but we are researching on a whole other level that we are focusing on different variables as how they affect the customer satisfaction in a restaurant.

2. Literature review

2.1 Food Quality:

The quality and the taste of food is essential because quality maintains your customer satisfaction. According to (Sudaria et al., 2019) quality of food which includes freshness, the proportion of food and taste has 61.7% influence on customer satisfaction. (Karki and Panthi, 2018). The value of food quality as a measure of customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry was emphasized by the researchers. As a result, five aspects of food quality have been identified. The term "freshness" typically refers to the crisp, juicy, and aromatic state of food. Previous research has identified food freshness as a significant intrinsic quality cue. One of the factors driving customer loyalty is food. According to the researchers, food is linked to variables such as the consumer and the context of eating. (Rozekhi et al., 2016). Food quality is the most important factor in restaurant selection. In casual-dining restaurants, food quality is a major determinant of customer loyalty. Food quality is related to customer food preference and demand. According to these studies, there may be a correlation between food quality and customer satisfaction. (Abdullah et al, 2018) The better services and food quality you provide, the more prominent you will be and the more satisfied your customers will be. Based on above literature review following alternative hypothesis has been developed.

H1: Hygiene Ambiance mediate relationship between food quality and customer satisfaction during COVID-19.

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2.3 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness has a positive impact on customers repurchase intention (Izzudin, and Novandarii, 2018), Brand awareness is one of the most important variables in the marketing, where brand awareness impacts customers because in this scenario awareness, the customer's memory to a brand becomes one of the factors emergences of the intention of customer to buy someone against a product (Rai et al., 2019). Brand awareness is the capacity of the given customer to recall or recognize that a certain brand belongs to the specific category of the products (Romaniuk et al., 2017). Brand recognition measures how easy or difficult it is for consumers to recognize brands. (Haque et al, 2018). According to Razak et al., (2020), several factors typically contribute to a brand's high brand awareness: it is constantly marketed, and it is synonymous with the presence and delivery of goods that hit different classes.

H2: Hygiene Ambiance mediate relationship between brand awareness and customer satisfaction during COVID-19.

2.3 Mediating Role of Hygiene Ambiance

Physical environment has the significant positive impact on the customer satisfaction (Cristo et al., 2017). Physical environment in the restaurants plays very important role in increasing the overall financial performance and helps in retaining customer and increases intention of customers to buy again and customer satisfaction also (Githiri, 2017).“Ambiance” is the most perceived dimension of the physical environment identified by (Ayazlar and Gun, (2017).Physical environment of the restaurant industry have the significant effect on quality perceptions of customers and customer satisfaction stated by (Cristo et al, 2017). Lighting has been taken as the most important ambient element as it permits the customers 'ability to see the food in its best possible way. So, managements should make sure that while designing the lighting of the restaurant, each and every table must have its own atmosphere in the terms of lighting as it leads to the customer satisfaction (Choi et al., 2017).

The aim of restaurant ambiance is to provide the customers a most comfortable environment and atmosphere while eating in a restaurant and fulfilling their expectations directly (Haque et al., 2018). Zamani et al., (2020), they conducted a research the impact of the factors of price, service quality, restaurant ambiance and food quality on customer satisfaction in Nepalese restaurants, and the study found that all these factors effected customer satisfaction. The main factors that impact customer satisfaction are restaurant ambiance, service quality, and food quality (Han and Ryu, 2009).

Figure

1:

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Proposed Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

The study's data source is 'Primary,' which means collecting research data directly from respondents. In other words, the primary source is the direct source of information about the topic or issue. In this case, data will be collected directly from participants through a formal adopted questionnaire focused on restaurant customer satisfaction. A research study's population consists of participants or respondents who share similar characteristics or traits. Business student's customer satisfaction at a restaurant chosen as the population of the study is made up of KFC Hyderabad, Pakistan.

This study is conducted on a size of ranging from 222. Finding with help of our primary data research method that is questionnaire, a total of 222 respondents answered our survey questionnaire and were customers of KFC Hyderabad and mainly residents of Hyderabad. In this analysis, a non-probability sampling approach will be used. Since there are time constraints in this analysis, convenience sampling, one of the methods of non-probability sampling, can help in data collection. Convenience sampling is both cost effective and time efficient. It will help in the collection of data in a timely and cost-effective manner. It would also reduce the issue of time constraints.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive analysis:

The questionnaire was distributed to the people of Hyderabad who visit/eat at KFC. Among the responses the female ratio was 48.6% (108 responses) and the male ratio was 51.4% (114 responses). Respondents aged between 18-20 years consist of 15.3%, the major portion of respondents belongs to the age group of 20-40 and consists of 62.6%, and respondents aged 40 or above years consist of 22.1%. Occupation is another category which was taken into consideration which was further divided into four sections including student, employed, unemployed and self- employed. Result showed that 33.8% people were students, 18% respondents were employed, 39.6% respondents were self-employed and remaining 8.6% people were unemployed. The Table 1 below shows all the results.

Table1: Respondent Profile

	Frequency	Percent
GENDER		
Male	114	51.6
Female	107	48.4
AGE		
18-20	33	14.9
20-40	139	62.9
40 or above	49	22.2
OCCUPATION		
Student	74	33.5
Unemployed	19	8.6
Employed	40	18.1
Self employed	88	39.8

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INCOME		
PKR 30,000-60,000	66	29.9
PKR 60,000-90,000	80	36.2
PKR 100,000 above	75	33.9

4.2 Reliability analysis

The reliability analysis has been used in this research to measure and check the reliability of the data collected and, on that basis, we conclude whether the data is reliable or not. We will use the value of Cronbach's Alpha to measure the reliability of the studied data. In our case, Cronbach's Alpha value of Food quality 0.709, N=4, Ambiance 0.759, N=4, Brand awareness 0.719, N=4, and Customer Satisfaction 0.738, N=4. All the studied variables are therefore reliable and conclusion can be drawn as the studied data is proved to be reliable using reliability analysis as shown in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Reliability analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Food Quality	.709	4
Hygiene Ambiance	.759	4
Brand Awareness	.719	4
Customer Satisfaction	.738	4

4.3 Hypothesis testing

4.3.1 Food Quality

You can notice the Table 3 indicates the mediating effect of ambiance between food quality and customer satisfaction. There are there effects are given including total effect, direct effect and indirect effect. Firstly, total effect of showed mediating effect mediating ambiance between food quality and customer satisfaction beta value 0.36 with p-value 0.001 is found to have positive and significant impact. Second, direct effect mediating ambiance between food quality and customer satisfaction with beta value 0.25 with p-value 0.000 is found to have positive and significant impact. Third, indirect effect mediating ambiance between food quality and customer satisfaction with beta value 0.11 with p-value 0.030 is found to have positive and significant impact. Hence, partial mediation effect has been revealed due to beta value reduced from 0.36 to 0.11 in presence of mediator ambiance.

Table 3: Food Quality (Mediation- SEM)

Hygiene Ambiance-> FQ	Beta value	Significant Value
Total Effect	0.36	0.001
Direct Effect	0.25	0.000
Indirect Effect	0.11	0.030

4.3.2 Brand Awareness

You can notice the Table 4 indicates the mediating effect of ambiance between brand awareness and customer satisfaction. There are there effects are given including total effect,

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direct effect and indirect effect. Firstly, total effect of showed mediating effect mediating ambiance between brand awareness and customer satisfaction beta value 0.42 with p-value 0.002 is found to have positive and significant impact. Second, direct effect mediating ambiance between brand awareness and customer satisfaction with beta value 0.35 with p-value 0.000 is found to have positive and significant impact. Third, indirect effect mediating ambiance between brand awareness and customer satisfaction with beta value 0.07 with p-value 0.000 is found to have positive and significant impact. Hence, partial mediation effect has been revealed due to beta value reduced from 0.42 to 0.07 in presence of mediator ambiance.

Table 4: Brand Awareness (Mediation- SEM)

Hygiene Ambiance-> BA	Beta value	Significant Value
Total Effect	0.42	0.002
Direct Effect	0.35	0.000
Indirect Effect	0.07	0.000

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Food Quality

According to the results above it was found that food quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction and if this data is compared with the past results authors like Sudira et al., (2019) found in them researches that Food quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction and has a favorable relationship. H1 is accepted. The quality and the taste of food are essential because quality maintains your customer satisfaction. The main features of food quality have been studied by Ko and Su (2015), who identified two factors which are correlated to customer satisfaction and products. The protection, hygiene and culinary arts categories relate to the goods category. The customer satisfaction category includes service quality and presentation. The definition of food quality varies from customer to customer, it's not possible to satisfy everyone because their views are inconsistent and they vary as everyone has a different perspective (Karki and Panthi 2018).

4.4.2 Brand Awareness

According to the results above it was found that Brand awareness has a significant impact on customer satisfaction and if this data is compared with the past results authors like Seo et al., (2015) have revealed in their studies that brand awareness has a significant impact on customer satisfaction hence H3 is accepted. Brand awareness is the capacity of the given customer to recall or recognize that a certain brand belongs to the specific category of the products (Romaniuk et al., 2017). Brand knowledge is determined by brand recognition and brand image. When a customer expresses a desire to buy a product/name, he or she effortlessly memorizes the brand. (Jamil et al., 2016). Everyone would be drawn to your brand if it is well-known and has made its mark in the headlines and in people's hearts.

1. Conclusion

In this study, we used primary data for finding out determinants of customer satisfaction in KFC food restaurant located in Hyderabad. Reliability test results show that the collected

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data is relevant and can be used for evaluating the mediating effect of hygiene ambiance between food quality, brand awareness and customer satisfaction during COVID-19. Furthermore, the result showed that all of the two independent variables is found to have partial mediating affect the customer satisfaction during COVID-19. The emphasis of this study is that top management of KFC Hyderabad, Pakistan should consider the hygiene ambiance during COVID-19 in order to have better market share in future.

5.1 Directions of future research

First, the present study was limited with four variables including food quality, brand awareness, hygiene ambiance and customer satisfaction during COVID-19. In future more variables can be added to research model in order to verify the behavior of individual's. Second, Serial mediation analysis and moderation of age and gender can be performance. Third, in future male and female comparative analysis can be applied. Lastly, in future study can be limited to youth only with more than the studied sample size.

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